

INTRAVASCULAR PLATELET ACTIVATION IN WOMEN WITH A THREATENED MISCARRIAGE AND ABORTED PREGNANCY WITH THE PRESENCE OF ANTIPHOSPHOLIPID ANTIBODIES

Kodirova Dildora Allayerovna

Ubaydullaeva Zukhra Ibragimovna

Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications
of Medical Workers, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
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Relevance: there is currently no doubt that circulating inflammatory factors and procoagulants, including homocysteine, play an important role in the pathogenesis of vascular disease. According to numerous studies, hyperhomocysteinemia occurs in approximately 5% of the population. The questions of the interaction of homocysteine with the system of intravascular blood coagulation and its role in the development of complications, such as miscarriage, require clarification.

It is important to note that homocysteine is highly toxic to cells. Elevated levels of homocysteine (hyperhomocysteinemia) play a negative role in vascular health. They can lead to damage and activation of endothelial cells, which significantly increases the risk of thrombosis.

Purpose of the study: was to study the dynamics of homocysteine levels and its relationship with the functional state of platelets in women with miscarriage.

Material and research methods: A prospective examination of 96 patients aged 18 to 26 years with miscarriage, unsuccessful IVF attempts and pregnancy complications in the form of preeclampsia, antenatal fetal death, and a history of fetoplacental circulation disorders was conducted.

The criterion for inclusion of patients was the presence of miscarriages, the state of preeclampsia, a history of aborted pregnancy. The exclusion criteria were the presence of pathologies of other organs and systems, such as pathology of the cardiovascular system, liver and pelvic organs.

Conclusions:

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that in women with miscarriage, changes in homocysteine metabolism and an increase in platelet aggregation activity are observed, which indicates their relationship.

Therefore, it is important to detect hyperhomocysteinemia in the early stages and provide appropriate therapy to reduce homocysteine levels, as well

as apply additional antithrombotic measures. It plays an important role in preventing miscarriage.

References:

1. Andrianova M. Yu., Roitman E. V., Isaeva A. M., Kolesnikova I. M., Nureev M. V. Pathogenetic and clinical substantiation of the complex prevention of hyperhomocysteinemia // Archives of Internal Medicine. 2014. No. 4.-C 51-56
2. Butenko A. V. Homocysteine: influence on biochemical processes in the human body // Young scientist. - 2016. - No. 1. — S. 78-82.
3. Genetic disorders of the coagulation cascade and homocysteine metabolism in the genesis of cerebral thrombosis / O. V. Sirotkina, Yu. V. Cherkas, A. V. Merkulova et al. // Med. academic journal. 2004. -T. 4, No. 4. - S. 23-28.
4. Kozlova, T.V. Hyperhomocysteinemia as a clinical manifestation of the risk of thrombosis / T.V. Kozlova // Wedge, medicine. 2005. - No. 2. - S. 9-11.
5. Clinical aspects of hypercysteinemia: monograph / ed. V.A. Snezhitsky, V.M. Pyrochkina [i dr.]. - GrGMU, 2011. - 292 p.
6. Makarenko, M.V. Management of pregnant women with fetal growth retardation syndrome on the background of thrombophilia and hyperhomocysteinemia / M.V. Makarenko // Family medicine. - 2014. - No. 3 (53). - S. 155.
7. Naumov, A.V. Homocysteine in the pathogenesis of microcirculatory and thrombotic complications / A.V. Naumov, T.N. Grinevich, V.M. Naidina // Thrombosis, hemostasis and rheology. - 2012. - T. 49, No. 4 - S. 9-19.
8. The level of homocysteine and indicators of platelet aggregation in patients with impaired cerebral circulation / Z. Sabaliauskiene, P. Gribauskas, V. Gaigalaite [et al.] // Therapeutic archive. - 2013. - T. 85, No. 3. - S. 75-79.
9. Shilova, A.N. Thromboembolism of the pulmonary arteries against the background of hyperhomocysteinemia / A.N. Shilova, A.A. Karpenko, Yu.E. Klevanets // Angiology and vascular surgery. - 2015. - V. 21, No. 1. - S. 25-28.
10. Shevchenko, O.P. Homocysteine is a new risk factor for atherosclerosis and thrombosis / O.P. Shevchenko // Klin. lab. diagnostics. - 2004. - No. 10. - S. 25-31.
11. Perla-Kajan J., Twardowski T., and Jakubowski H. Mechanisms of homocysteine toxicity in humans // Amino Acids (2007) 32: 561–572
12. Yilmaz N. Relationship between paraoxonase and homocysteine: crossroads of oxidative diseases // Arch Med Sci 1, February / 2012. P. 138–153.